

LEXICAL AND GRAMMATICAL TRANSFORMATION IN THE PROCESS OF LITERARY TRANSLATION

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ABSTRACT

The paper deals with the study of lexico-grammatical transformations in the translation of literary text from English into Russian. Despite the large number of works covering this issue, the problem of translating literary texts is not dismissed. There is a need to systematize and study the types of lexical and grammatical transformations, used in translating literary texts, in practice. The authors of the study make an attempt of full revelation and comprehensive study of the translation transformations used to achieve the adequacy of translation to the original. In the process of work, the features of literary translation are revealed, as well as peculiarities of using transformations in literary translation; the practical expediency of using these transformations in the translation of the chosen work is determined, and the quantitative and statistical analysis of the translation transformations in the considered passages taken from the work is carried out. To solve the tasks in this paper, the following methods were used: comparative analysis of the comparison of the translation text with the text of the original work, transformational, quantitative, statistical analyses.

Keywords: translation, translation transformation, adequate translation, lexical additions, permutations, grammatical substitutions, narrowing, generalization, compensation.

INTRODUCTION

Translation is the communication of the meaning of a source-language text by means of an equivalent target-language text. Translation implies correct and comprehensive rendering what is expressed in one language by means of the other language. The present work is focused on the grammatical transformations that are vital while converting linguistic units of the source text into the text of the target language. According to the definition by V.N. Komissarov, literary translation is such a kind of translation, which is supposed to create a literary text in the target language and influence the reader emotionally and aesthetically. For this reason a lot of critics

believe that the literary translation is a piece of art, which is dominated by masters only who follow only aesthetic criteria while making a translation. The preceding considerations support the notion that literary translation is both a language and a literary phenomenon. Literary translation is intended to render the meaning and message of the original text in order to make the translated text more creative. The main purpose of the translation is to achieve adequacy. The main task of an interpreter at achieving adequacy is to skillfully produce various translation transformations so that the text of the translation as accurately as possible conveys all the information contained in the original text while observing the appropriate norms of the target language.

1. The term “transformation” in translation studies is used to show the relationship between the source and target language expressions, the substitution in the process of translation of one form of expression by another, a substitution that we figuratively call conversion or transformation. Thus, the operations described below (translation transformations) are essentially inter-lingual operations of meaning “re-expression”. The main purpose of the translation is to achieve adequacy. The main task of an interpreter at achieving adequacy is to skillfully produce various translation transformations so that the text of the translation as accurately as possible conveys all the information contained in the original text while observing the appropriate norms of the target language. At present, there are many works devoted to translation studies, which concern the concept of translation transformation and classification. The theoretical basis for this study was the classification of translation transformations given by V.N. Komissarov, L.S. Barkhudarov. L.S. Barkhudarov notes that, first of all, the highest possible level of translation equivalence of the text should be achieved (Barkhudarov,1975). V.N. Komissarov considers the translation transformations to be “transformational change by means of which it is possible to make a transition from the original units to the translation units”¹. The translational transformations, in his opinion, have a formal and semantic character, transforming both the form and the meaning of the source units. The adequacy of the translation is always connected with the skills of a competent statement of the translation problem and the ability to make the necessary transformational translation. The main objective of this study is to comprehensively study the lexical and grammatical transformations on the material of the translation of the literary text of Aldous Huxley’s work “Eyeless in Gaza”. Aldous Huxley is one of the recognized masters of the so-called “intellectual novel”, which became widespread in the 20th century. Huxley himself called his works to be “the novels of ideas”. The confrontations of completely opposite viewpoints and

¹ (Komissarov, 2002).

paradoxical systems of thought engenders an unexpected satirical effect in his works. “Eyeless in Gaza” is a novel written by Huxley in 1936, which became one of the main creative performance of the writer. The work by A. Huxley has been translated into Russian by M. Lovin. It is supposed that the results of this study will serve to solve the following problems in the field of translation studies:

1. Reveal the features of literary translation, as well as the peculiarities of using transformations in li translation;
2. Reveal the translation transformations in the source text of the chosen work;
3. Determine the practical expediency of using these transformations in the translation of the chosen work;
4. Carry out quantitative and statistical analysis of the translation transformations in the considered extracts taken from the work;
5. Reveal inadequacies and mistakes of the translator and give our own translation.

The practical value of this work lies in the possibility of further use of the material for studying translation transformations in the course of theory and practice of translation.

METHODS

We have chosen the novel by A. Huxley “Eyeless in Gaza” as an object of study. The actual research material is presented on the basis of the following principles: •case study of the work; •existence of the translation that has entered into “gold reserves” of foreign literature; •conceptual intensesness of the text snippets, chosen to analyze transformations. Their high position in semantic structure of the work. Since the scope of this work does not allow of full comprehending of the text case of examples, in most cases there are the combinations of utterances of the source text and the translation, but the analysis was carried out with consideration of the integral context of the literary translation. The following methods were used in the work: comparative analysis of contrasting the translation text with the text of the original work, transformational, quantitative, statistical analyses.

RESULTS

To conduct a quantitative analysis, we have chosen the key “textemes” of the novel:

1. Scene on the roof of a Mediterranean villa (Chapter III);
2. Anthony’s attempt to generalize his understanding of the modern world and the concept of personality (Chapter XI);

3. An episode in the London Library (Chapter XXVII), after a painful face-to-face meeting with Brian's bride;

4. Miller's sermon in Mexico (Chapter XLIX).

Huxley entrusted him with expressing the ideas that would eventually become the key for his understanding the world. The results obtained during the research can be more specifically observed in the following diagram: complex substitution concretization omission addition grammatical substitution metaphorical translation modulation transcription and transliteration transposition sentence fragmentation generalization antonymic translation sentence integration compensation.

DISCUSSION

Rendering from one language into another requires the use of various transformations. All kinds of transformations (explication, lexical additions, permutations, grammatical replacement, sentence fragmentation and integration, semantic development, narrowing, generalization, compensation, etc.) are used in translating fictional literature, however, the choice of these or those methods directly depends on the chosen by a translator strategy or model of translation. Transliteration and transcription are the most frequently used methods of transformation when translating proper names. The methods of translation of the names of different teachings and their followers combine both transliteration with transcription and historically developed forms of translation. The original text of the novel comprises interesting examples of the transliteration of name from Russian into English, which the translator translated back. Concretization and generalization are, perhaps, the most common methods of translation. This is primarily due to the fact that the semantic field of meanings in different languages does not always coincide: the translator specified the word earth, thus disclosing its second dictionary meaning: earth-red (p.15) -clay-red (p. 21). There are methods of concretization aimed at disclosing of the context of the original. This kind of concretization is close to addition, with the only difference that the clarifying unit substitutes for the unit of the original language.

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